

Effect of Electric Field on Tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ Ions in Agar Gel

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Manuscript received 16 April 1993, revised 16 September 1994, accepted 19 October 1994

The tracer-diffusion coefficient and mobility of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ions in 2.5% agar gel containing sodium nitrate, potassium nitrate, sodium sulphate and potassium sulphate solutions (0.001 M) have been determined at 25° by zone electromigration in presence of d.c. field of different intensities. A non-Gaussian distribution of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ion in d.c. field resulted in two unequal values of tracer-diffusion coefficients D_1 and D_2 in and against the field direction, which increases with increase in intensity and duration of field application. A suitable mechanism is suggested to explain the observed results.

A number of works have been done on diffusion of a number of ions in various electrolyte solutions in aqueous medium¹ and in gel medium² by different techniques. Further, the broadening of the boundaries in zone electrophoresis was first studied by Ogston³. Later, a theory of accelerated diffusion was developed by Mysels⁴, Mysels and Scholten⁵ and by Bak and Kauman⁶. Chemla and Arnika⁷ observed a unique asymmetry of the migrating ions while studying electromigration both in fused salts and agar gel media, as a means of isotope separation. The present work was selected to study the effect of d.c. field on tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ions in 2.5% agar gel containing sodium nitrate, potassium nitrate, sodium sulphate and potassium sulphate solutions (0.001 M) at 25°. Further, the effect of intensity and duration of d.c. field on tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ions was studied.

Results and Discussion

In simple tracer-diffusion, i.e. in the absence of electric field, a Gaussian distribution of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ions was obtained thus giving a single value of tracer-diffusion coefficient⁸. Whereas in the presence of d.c. field, the central zone migrates to a certain distance depending upon the nature of the ions, field strength and period of field applied. From the migrated distance, the ionic mobility of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ions was calculated by using equation (2) (See Ex-

perimental). The theoretical value of ionic mobility was calculated from the relation, $V^0 = \lambda^0/F$, where λ^0 is the limiting equivalent conductivity at specified temperature and F the Faraday's constant. The values of ionic mobility of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ ions in all the electrolytes studied are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—IONIC MOBILITY (V_{expt}) OF $^{131}\text{I}^-$ IONS AT 25° IN DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTE SOLUTIONS (0.001 M) IMMOBILISED IN 2.5% AGAR GEL AT DIFFERENT APPLIED VOLTAGES

$$V_{\text{theo}} = 7954 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ V}^{-1}$$

Voltage applied V cm ⁻²	NaNO ₃	KNO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₄	K ₂ SO ₄
2.307	5 026	3 402	4 957	3 927
4 615	5 651	5 813	5 120	5 054

The migrated central zone spreads unequally on both sides giving an symmetric Gaussian distribution (Fig.1). Thus, two unequal values of electrodiffusion coefficients D_1 and D_2 in and against the field direction were obtained from the slope of the plot of $\log a$ vs x^2 (Fig. 2). Results obtained for different intensities and period of field application are given in Tables 2 and 3 for all the electrolytes studied. It is evident from the results that under similar conditions of temperature and concentration of the electrolyte, both the values of D_1 and D_2 , in and against the field direction are greater than simple

Fig. 1. Electrodiffusion of ^{131}I ions in $10^{-3} M$ KNO_3 solution in 2.5% agar gel at 25° under d.c. field (2.307 V cm^{-1}) for 4 h : (---) centre of gravity (\bar{X}) = 10.4 cm and (---) model point (X) = 10.8 cm.

tracer diffusion (D_0), i.e. in the absence of electric field, $D_2 > D_1 > D_0$. Further, it is observed (Tables 2 and 3) that with increase in intensity and duration of field, electrodiffusion coefficients of ^{131}I ions increase. This is due to the fact that ionic mobility increases with increase in field intensity resulting in increase in electrodiffusion coefficient.

TABLE 2—TRACER-DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT OF $^{131}\text{I}^-$ IONS IN 2.5% AGAR GEL AT 25° IN PRESENCE OF d.c. FIELD

Electrolyte	Field applied V cm^{-1}	$10^5 D \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	Period (h)		
			2	3	4
NaNO_3	2.307	D_0	2.051	2.051	2.051
	2.307	D_1	2.276	2.705	3.425
	2.307	D_2	2.809	3.308	4.132
	4.615	D_0	2.051	2.051	2.051
	4.615	D_1	2.454	3.629	4.778
	4.615	D_2	3.492	4.924	6.250
KNO_3	2.307	D_0	2.066	2.066	2.066
	2.307	D_1	2.114	2.826	3.015
	2.307	D_2	2.541	3.392	5.099
	4.615	D_0	2.066	2.066	2.066
	4.615	D_1	2.985	4.083	5.533
	4.615	D_2	3.413	5.496	6.424

TABLE 3—TRACER-DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT OF $^{131}\text{I}^-$ IONS IN 2.5% AGAR GEL AT 25° IN PRESENCE OF d.c. FIELD

Electrolyte (0.001 M)	Field applied V cm^{-1}	$10^5 \times D \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	Period (h)		
			2	3	4
Na_2SO_4	2.307	D_0	2.038	2.038	2.038
	2.307	D_1	2.102	2.289	3.420
	2.307	D_2	2.239	3.596	4.375
	4.615	D_0	2.038	2.038	2.038
	4.615	D_1	2.858	4.601	5.166
	4.615	D_2	3.758	5.304	6.672
K_2SO_4	2.307	D_0	2.042	2.042	2.042
	2.307	D_1	2.122	2.261	3.756
	2.307	D_2	2.348	3.790	4.781
	4.615	D_0	2.042	2.042	2.042
	4.615	D_1	3.358	3.918	4.835
	4.615	D_2	4.629	5.121	6.597

Fig. 2. Electrodiffusion of ^{131}I ions in $10^{-3} M$ KNO_3 solution in 2.5% agar gel at 25° under d.c. field (2.307 V cm^{-1}) for 4 h : (●) D_1 in the field direction and (○) D_2 against the field direction.

Earlier studies on electrodiffusion^{3,6} revealed that the effective diffusion coefficient (D_{field}) is the sum of a simple diffusion coefficient (D_0) and a term D_e due to electrodiffusion, where D_e is the function of the square of the electric field (E) and the product of the charge (C) and mobility (V) of the ions,

$$D_{\text{field}} = D_0 + D_e$$

$$D_e = V^2 E^2 / 2K$$

where K is constant.

In the present work, a further correlation $\pm \delta$ to the electrodiffusion term, D_e , operative in the two directions, would be required and the effective diffusion coefficients may be given by

$$D_1 = D_0 + D_e - \delta$$

$$D_2 = D_0 + D_e + \delta$$

This is the reason that D_1 and D_2 are unequal in and against the field direction. The two unequal values of electrodiffusion coefficient can also be explained by the fact that in ordinary diffusion, both the partner ions move with a common speed so that there is no charge separation. But in electrodiffusion, the two ions diffuse in opposite directions with their characteristic mobilities which are proportional to their tracer-diffusion coefficients. This results in a charge separation which lasts till the formation of new ion-atmosphere at these sites. During this relaxation period, an intense electric field due to charge separation acts in opposite direction to the applied fields. This is effective upto a distance of molecular dimensions. This reverse field would favour larger Brownian displacement in the opposite direction. The integrated effect of this over a finite period gives rise to asymmetry in Brownian displacement in the two directions as observed in the present study.

With the help of relaxation and electrophoretic effects, the two unequal values of electrodiffusion coefficient can be further explained. It has been postulated⁹ that in and against the field direction, there is a small but finite difference between the size of ion-atmosphere ($1/x$) and/or the relaxation time (τ) of the diffusing ion in occupying holes in and against the field direction. This is valid for each jump of the ions. This may result in difference between diffusion coefficients D_1 and D_2 measured at the end of the finite period. Further, a mechanism for electrodiffusion of ions is envisaged. The ions diffusing in the direction of field has a relatively longer relaxation time (τ_1) in jumping out of the old atmosphere and in the reverse direction has

relatively shorter relaxation time (τ_2) as its old positively charged atmosphere tends to move with it under the action of the field. This concept also implies a difference in ion-atmosphere sizes ($1/x_1$ and $1/x_2$).

Depending upon these facts, the final expressions for the electrodiffusion coefficient D_1 and D_2 in and against the field respectively takes the form⁹,

$$D_1 = D_0 + D_e + \frac{fvE}{x_1 \sqrt{\tau_1 K}}$$

$$D_2 = D_0 + D_e + \frac{fvE}{x_2 \sqrt{\tau_2 K}}$$

where $x_1 \sqrt{\tau_1 K} > x_2 \sqrt{\tau_2 K}$ and f is a dimensionless factor and other symbols have their usual significance. From the above equations, it is evident that when the relaxation time is greater along the field direction, there is less increase in diffusion coefficient D_1 and when relaxation time is shorter in the reverse direction, a large increase in D_2 values is observed.

Fig. 3. Electrophoresis unit: (1) agar gel, (2) electrolyte solution, (3) thermostated water and (4) Pt electrode.

Experimental

The apparatus used for determining the ionic mobility and tracer-diffusion of labelled ions under the influence of electric field is similar to that of Kendell's one-dimensional 'zone' electrophoresis¹⁰ (Fig. 3). It consisted of a Pyrex tube (70–80 cm \times 1 cm dia), the two ends of which were fitted with two auxiliary tubes one at each end. These two auxiliary tubes contained one platinum electrode each. An electrolyte solution of the same concentration (as in gel phase) was allowed to circulate through the auxiliary tubes in order to minimise the effect of change in concentration of the electrolyte due to electrolysis. Heating due to electromigration was minimised by circulating cooled water through an

outer jacket at a desired temperature from a thermostat.

A 2.5% agar gel containing the electrolyte solution (0.001 M) was prepared by heating. The gel while hot, was poured into the electromigration tube corked at one end to prevent the flow-out. A little more than half of the tube was filled with the gel and kept in the vertical position in order to let out air bubbles entrapped in the gel column. After setting up the gel in the tube, the gel column was brought out to the other end of the tube by tilting and its upper concave gel column was removed. The tube was again kept in vertical position and on this plain surface, a narrow zone (1–2 cm) of the agar gel containing the labelled ions (i.e. ^{131}I ions) was deposited. After setting of this zone, the upper concave surface was removed by cutting. Above this zone, rest of the tube was again filled by the agar gel containing the same electrolyte of the same concentration. This was allowed to set by keeping the tube in vertical position. Precautions were taken in making a good contact between the zone and gel column. The tube was then loaded into the electrophoresis unit in horizontal position. A stabilised d.c. high voltage source provided the voltage necessary for the electromigration. The position of the zone and the period of electromigration were so adjusted that the zone migrates towards the farthest end without going beyond the gel column. After passing the current for a definite period at a particular voltage, the tube was taken out of the unit and scanned by a G.M. counter to find out the approximate position of the migrated zone. This portion of the gel column was sliced into 5 mm long samples. These samples were transferred to aluminium planchelets and dried. The radioactivity of each sample was measured by using an end-window G.M. counter under the conditions of constant geometry. A plot of radioactivity vs distance from the origin gives an asymmetric Gaussian distribution with a negative skew in the direction of field (Fig. 2). The distance \bar{X} between the centre of gravity of the curve and the origin is the length migrated by the labelled ions and is given by the relation,

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum a_i x_i}{\sum a_i} \quad (1)$$

where a_i is the activity of concentration of labelled species at a distance x_i from the origin. The mobility is calculated by the relation,

$$V = \frac{\bar{X}}{t} \frac{1}{V} \quad (2)$$

where t is the period of field application and V is the voltage across the gel column of 1 cm.

The diffusion of the narrow zone into semi-infinite columns (of length $\pm a$) on either side of the origin ($x = 0$) corresponds to the boundary conditions,

$$C_{(0,0)} = C_0, C_{(x,0)} = 0, C_{(a,t)} = 0$$

The required function $C_{(x,t)}$ is provided by the integral of Fick's second law¹¹,

$$C_{(x,t)} = \frac{C_0}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} \exp(-x^2/4Dt) \quad (3)$$

By taking model point of the asymmetry Gaussian curve as the migrated origin, $\log a$ vs x^2 was plotted (Fig. 3), where x is the distance of the samples from model point. The distance of model point from origin (X) is calculated by the relation⁹,

$$X = L + \frac{a_L}{a_p + a_1} C \quad (4)$$

where L is the distance of that sample from the origin which contains the highest concentration or radioactivity a_L , while a_p and a_1 are the activities in the samples preceding and leading to it, and C is the interval (0.5 cm).

References

1. R. MILLS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 852; O. BERNARD, W. KUNZ, P. TURO and I. BIUMI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1992, **96**, 398; T. HASHITANI and K. TANAKA, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday. Trans. 1*, 1983, **79**, 1765.
2. S. BALUJA and B. M. SHUKLA, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1984, **37**, 107; S. F. PATIL, N. S. RAJUKAR and A. V. BORHADE, *Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 1991, **150**, 189; A. L. SLADE, A. E. CREMER and H. C. THOMAS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2840.
3. A. G. OGSTON, *Nature*, 1946, **57**, 193.
4. K. J. MYSELS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **24**, 371.
5. K. J. MYSELS and P. C. SCHOLTEN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1961, **57**, 764.
6. T. K. BAK and W. G. KAUMAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 1109.
7. H. J. ARNIKAR and M. CHEMLA, *Radioisotopes Sci. Res.*,

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- 1958, **2**, 421; H. J. ARNIKAR, *Ann. Phys*, 1959, **4**, 1291;
H. J. ARNIKAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **11**, 249.
8. S. BALUJA, R. TRIPATHI and B. M. SHUKLA, *Proc. Ann. Conv.*, 1981, S. BALUJA, R. N. SINGH, R. TRIPATHI and B. M. SHUKLA, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 1985, **94**, 233.
9. H. J. ARNIKAR, *Indian J Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 1.
10. J. KENDELL, *J Phys. Rev.*, 1959, **31**, 389; *J. Am. Chem Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 3114.
11. J. CRANKS, "The Mathematics of Diffusion", Clarendon, Oxford.

